

Modelling and subtractive synthesis of a virtual violin

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Abstract—

Although solutions to the challenge of binaural artificial recreation of audio spatialisation exist in the Computer Music domain, a review of the area suggests that a comprehensive, generic, accurate and efficient toolset is required; hence this paper will deal with automated sound creation using sound synthesis. The entire setup was implemented using Csound. Csound implements many synthesis techniques unavailable through other means, such as user-controlled physical modeling. A number of Csound opcodes is presented to satiate this necessity. It provides a platform for creating customized instruments to produce the required sounds and a player that renders the sound according to the requirements. It provides a powerful base for performing signal processing functions like envelope shaping, filtering and mixing (additive and subtractive synthesis of sounds with disparate parameters). The final output is the product of the filter output that produces the sound of required frequencies and envelope shaping function that controls the amplitude. The utmost use of this research work is the optimum reduction in human interference without compensating with any of the efficient results obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Realizing music by digital computer involves synthesizing audio signals with discrete points or samples representative of continuous waveforms. There are many ways to do this, each affording a different manner of control [1]. Direct synthesis generates waveforms by sampling a stored function representing a single cycle; additive synthesis generates the many partials of a complex tone, each with its own loudness envelope; subtractive synthesis begins with a complex tone and filters it [2].

Since comprehensive moment-by-moment specification of sound can be tedious, control is gained in two ways; first from the definition of instruments in the orchestra [3]; and second by rendering the instruments predefined in orchestra according to the scheduling of the events from the score [4]. An orchestra is a set of statements that are written to direct the production of sound according to the specifications required, while a score is a body of data which that program can react to in order to determine the order in which the user wants to play the sound. For instance: whether a rise-time characteristic is a

fixed constant in an instrument, or a variable of each depends on how the user wants to control it [5].

The instruments in a Csound orchestra are defined in simple syntaxes may be used as the base to synthesize complex audio processing routines. A score passed to this orchestra contains numerically coded pitch and control information, in standard numeric score format. Although many users are content with this format, higher level score processing languages are often convenient as it provides more controlling options and improves the readability.

SUBTRACTIVE SYNTHESIS

There are three basic elements to any sound: Pitch (base frequency), Volume (or loudness) and Timbre (also called tone or brightness).

In subtractive Synthesis a basic waveform is created, rich in harmonics. The harmonic structure is then altered by removing certain harmonics (hence 'Subtractive Synthesis') but allowing the rest to pass on to an amplifier so that the volume of the signal can be altered. The three basic electrical components that control these functions are the oscillator (*source*), *filter* and *amplifier* (as shown in figure-1).

Fig-1: Block diagram for generic subtractive synthesis

The oscillator serves a dual function in the subtractive synthesizer [6]. The pitch of any tone is generated by the oscillator, the value of that pitch being determined by a controller device. The second function of the oscillator is to generate a waveform rich in harmonics, producing a basic timbre which can be shaped by careful use of the filter. To apply the subtractive synthesis technique to the generation of a violin sound the source is a basic sine wave of fixed frequency and the filter that approximates the response of the violin. The digital waveform of the sine wave has to be band limited, in order to have a Spectrum without aliasing. s

Upon generating a source to be filtered to the required “spectral richness” is that it has to be a band limited signals due to the restrictions imposed by the sampling frequency of the system (Nyquist criterion).

Synthesis

Csound synthesizes the transcribed music, providing the Score and the Orchestra files upon successful compilation of the written statements by the C-Sound compiler. The score is written in terms of pitch, onset and duration of the notes though it can also modified and written catering to the needs of the user based on whatever parameter of the sound that needs to be controlled. However, in order to replicate the melodious sound of the violin optimum use of the envelope and the timbre are essential [11].

The Timbre

The timbre of the note is characteristic of the instrument. It defines the sound that is synthesized in a wholesome manner. Any string instrument is characterized by its attack time (the sound produced when the string is struck), after the attack time the sound decays to a steady amplitude (decay time) and steady amplitude is maintained for some time(sustain time) and finally is released and the subsequent volume of the note fades to zero(release time). The wavetable synthesis is considered taking advantage of the typical structure of the signal (sine in this case). The Figure shows this structure, which is the basic waveform, repeated in time at the pitch frequency. The wavetable synthesis exploits this property repeating the basic waveform in time and multiplying its amplitude by the envelope [12]. For each note the basic waveform is extracted from the original signal and stored in a table. In this way more than one instrument can played in the same song since the synthesis follows the timbre changing among octaves.

Fig-2. Periodic waveform of a string instrument

Considering figure 3, the table is completed with the original samples between 2 consecutive maxima via the sustain part of the note. One development of the system will focus on the attack synthesis as it often determines how similar the sound produced will be to violin (in this case) .

The envelope

The case of “lineseg” envelope is considered here. The Csound function “linseg” traces linear segments between defined points’ .The note’s envelope is divided in 4 parts: attack, decay, sustain, release. The information about the onset and the duration of a note is already known from the collector. The segmentation of the signal in notes makes the calculation of the envelope’s parameters a trivial task.[13] Although different shapes should be considered for different instrument. In the figure shown, for instance, the thresholds for the envelope segmentation are 50% of the maximum amplitude for the beginning of the sustain part and 20% for the beginning of the release. These values fit particularly well to the piano, which typical note’s shape is shown below, however they should be optimized for different instruments.

Fig -3. Attack, Decay, Sustain, Release.

The amplitude information can be very important to detect missed notes. Since the onset time is determined from the pitch information, a sequence of two same notes could lead to only one lasting for the duration of the two[14]. Therefore, if the amplitude rises twice in the same note, we can assume that another note has been played.

ATTACK - The envelope "opens" from zero amplitude and shoots to maximum (in this case. It may also open from an amplitude level and reach another value higher than the first value). The time taken for this process is known as Attack time. An Attack time of zero means the envelope goes from zero to full instantly (ie sharp attack). Increasing the Attack time would make the process to slow down.

DECAY - The envelope then drops from Maximum to the Sustain level. This is known by the Decay time. A Decay time of zero means the envelope goes from maximum to sustain instantly. Increasing the Decay time means that this will happen more slowly.

SUSTAIN - The continuing envelope just remains at the Sustain level. This is set by Sustain level.

RELEASE - The envelope then drops from the Sustain level to zero. This is controlled by Release time. A Release time of zero means that this will happen instantly. Increasing the Release time means that this will happen more slowly.

Each sound is identified by its unique ADSR times. In this case, this will try to reproduce the characteristic attack ,sustain, decay and release pattern of the violin sound. These patterns depend both on the interpreter and the music style.

The final sound is computed by multiplying the output of the filter with the envelope shaping function in the time domain:

$$v(t) = F(s(t))e(t)$$

Where $v(t)$ is the final violin sound, $s(t)$ is the source output, $F(.)$ denotes the composite action of the filter bank and $e(t)$ is the envelope shaping function[15].

We employed a method of summing of the sounds got from by linen and expon envelopes and providing this as the input to the basic sine wave oscillator to produce the violin sound emulating the violin sound by varying the attack and release time limits requisitely.

Fig -4: Output wave form of the synthesized violin sound

Introduction of vibrato effect

The well known vibrato effect of the violin sound was emulated by introducing some pitch jitter, through the addition of a low frequency and small amplitude sinusoid to the fundamental frequency of each saw tooth signal, as illustrated in figure

$$F_{vib}(n) = F_0 + A_v \sin(2\pi \frac{f_v}{F_s} n)$$

In order to approximate the frequency response of the violin body to the forces in the bridge, a filter bank is used. Each filter is a “Regalia-Mitra” second order equalizer filter, and is based on an all pass filter, three adders and two gains. This structure is advantageous because the frequency, bandwidth and gain parameters are easy to change [10].

Each filter has a transfer function:

$$a = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \tan(\Omega/2)}{1 + \tan \Omega/2} & K \geq 1 \\ \frac{K - \tan(\Omega/2)}{K + \tan \Omega/2} & K < 1 \end{cases}$$

Where Ω is the normalized 3 dB bandwidth, K the gain and ω_0 the normalized central frequency of the filter. For the modeling of the violin body response, a filter bank comprising three of the above mentioned equalization filters was used, with center frequencies 300Hz, 700Hz and 3000Hz. The 3dB bandwidths were 20, 60 and 500 Hz and the gains 11, 20 and 40.

CONCLUSION

The subtractive synthesis technique was successfully utilized for the generation of a violin sound. A vibrato effect based on a slow modulation of the period was included to yield a more realistic sound. More realism could be achieved by fine tuning the source and filter blocks. In particular, Addition of more equalizers to the filter bank thus makes the approximation to the violin response more precise. The combining parameters (amplitudes and detuning) can still be optimized. The advantage of sound synthesis is that it saves the memory used for saving the recordings by recreating the sound from the C-Sound Orchestra and Score files. It is note worthy that these files are only text files so considerable memory is saved and the vitality of saving memory increases with the quality of sound saved. The higher the quality the more the memory required to save it.

When many instruments are created and a suitable note file is generated then the sound produced would resemble that of an orchestra. Thus real world music like the background music effects of the films can be generated in C-Sound in the occupying space in the order as that of a text file.

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